

MultiXscale

Intermediate report on Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

MultiXscale Deliverable 7.2
Deliverable Type: Report
Delivered in December, 2024

MultiXscale
EuroHPC Centre of Excellence for
Multiscale Modelling

Co-funded by
the European Union

Acknowledgement

Funded by the European Union. This work has received funding from the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 101093169.

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Project and Deliverable Information

Project Title Project Ref. Project Website EuroHPC Project Officer	MultiXscale: EuroHPC Centre of Excellence for Multiscale Modelling Grant Agreement 101093169 https://www.multixscale.eu Dr. Matteo Mascagni
Deliverable ID Deliverable Nature Dissemination Level Contractual Date of Delivery Actual Date of Delivery	D7.2 Report Public Project Month 24 (31 st December, 2024) 30 th December, 2024
Description of Deliverable	Report covering all tasks performed during the execution of WP7.

Document Control Information

Document	Title:	Intermediate report on Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation
	ID:	D7.2
	Version:	As of December, 2024
	Status:	Accepted by SC
	Available at: Document history:	https://www.multixscale.eu/deliverables Internal Project Management Link
Review	Review Status:	Reviewed
Authorship	Written by:	Elisabeth Ortega, Pedro Fernández, Susana Hernández (HPCNow!)
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Document Keywords

Keywords:	MultiXscale, HPC, software, applications , infrastructure
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30th December, 2024

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Executive Summary

This intermediate report shows the advances of the four tasks that composes the Work Package 7 (Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication). It is written following the Work Package structure and following the evolution and future plans of each task.

Task 7.1 (Scientific applications provisioned on demand) focuses on the production of an easy-to-use platform to provide the codes generated during the execution of the project, among other software packages. The current status of this task is promising, with a solution tailored for AWS ParallelCluster [already merged in AWS HPC recipes repository](#). Future plans involve the integration of EESSI software tool in Open OnDemand HPC portal, lowering the entry barrier to users with low experience in the use of terminals to manage the cluster.

Task 7.2 (Dissemination and communication activities), points to the latest changes in dissemination and press strategy, and lists the events already attended and the planned ones for 2025. There are two points to highlight. First, the number of events attended is quite big, considering that in all of these a member of the consortium presented a talk or a poster, conducted a tutorial or performed a demo. Additionally, the dissemination team joined forces with their analogues from other Centers of Excellence to organize two workshops at the HiPEAC conference that will take place in Barcelona, on January 2025, with a strong presence of women on the stage.

Tasks 7.3 (Sustainability) and 7.4 (Industry-oriented training activities) started to be elaborated at slow pace, as those requires further exploration of legal entities able to sustain the project (Task 7.3) and more advances from the technical and scientific team before providing targeted training sessions.

In summary, the future plans on dissemination activities, the deployment of a provisioning solution and the strong collaboration with the other Centers of Excellence, keep MultiXscale aligned to the original plan.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This document covers the progress on the execution of the tasks inside Work Package 7 (WP7) “Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication”. The outcomes of the project do not stop with the creation of new codes and new tools to make them accessible to the community, a strategic dissemination, communication and exploitation action should follow the scientific and technical progress, creating awareness of the solutions provided and facilitating their access to a smooth adoption in the academy and industry.

1.2 Target audience

The expected target of this deliverable is quite broad. On one side, this deliverable aims to provide an update of the dissemination, communication and exploitation activities to the followers of the Center of Excellence (CoE) (other CoEs, NCCs, project monitors and ambassadors,...). This deliverable also targets the other members of the CoE participating in the different Work Packages, who can provide feedback on the dissemination activities and participation in events to improve them in the future. Lastly, this deliverable also targets the general public, who will be informed about the past and future plans in the MultiXscale CoE.

1.3 Deliverable outline

This deliverable has six sections:

- Section 1 - Introduction: it is the current section of the document, where the scope, the target audience, and the contributions of the partners involved in elaborating the manuscript are described.
- Sections 2-5. Those sections will describe the work done in the four tasks contained in WP7:
 - **Task 7.1** - Scientific applications provisioned on demand.
 - **Task 7.2** - Dissemination and communication activities.
 - **Task 7.3** - Sustainability.
 - **Task 7.4** - Industry-oriented training activities.
- Section 6 includes an enumeration of the conclusions that can be extracted from the evolution of the WP7 during the first half of the project and a view to the future.

1.4 Partner contributions

For the elaboration of this document, Pedro Fernández, Susana Hernández and Elisabeth Ortega (HPCNow!) contributed equally. Neja Šamec (NIC) contributed in the redaction of specific sections and Alan Ó Cais (UB) performed the revision of the final document.

Partners HPCNow, NIC, UB have contributed as planned to the ongoing Tasks 7.1, 7.2, and 7.3 of this deliverable. Task 7.4 is led by HPCNow and is in the early planning stages, with contributions from Leronardo expected in the remainder of RP2 and in RP3.

2 Evolution and current status of Task 7.1

The aim of Task 7.1 (Scientific application provisioned on demand) is the provision of scientific software in compute services commonly used by industrial users. This effort includes making this software more accessible to those end users.

We provide the scientific software via the European Environment for Scientific Software Installations (EESSI) stack [1], that enables on-demand distribution of optimized software. Users do not require any software compilation and optimization knowledge, since EESSI is capable of autodetecting the microarchitecture of the host to deliver the correct binary.

In this task we have worked on delivering the EESSI software stack to Amazon Web Services (AWS) for HPC workloads, with a direct and fruitful collaboration with them. In addition, we are now starting a new collaboration with the Open OnDemand team to include EESSI in their service registry, which should increase the accessibility to and ease the usage of scientific software, both in the cloud and in HPC centers.

2.1 AWS ParallelCluster integration

Running High Performance Computing (HPC) workloads requires not only knowledge of the specific scientific application, but may also require one to consider computer engineering aspects, like networking, shared filesystems, batch scheduler, compilation of applications, etc.

In a Supercomputer, much of this has already been taken care of, and the users can focus on executing their workloads. On the contrary, this has not generally been the case in the cloud where the user was responsible for all configuration of the provisioned hardware. However, for some years now, there have been approaches to ease the deployment of HPC infrastructure. AWS ParallelCluster [2] is one such approach. It is an open-source cluster management tool from AWS that allows the deployment of a configured and ready-to-use HPC cluster in the AWS cloud.

Other tools exist, like Magic Castle [3], which is cloud-agnostic. The integration of EESSI with Magic Castle is detailed in D6.2: "Infrastructure to support training activities". However, AWS ParallelCluster is widely used and has a lot of visibility in the HPC industry. Therefore, collaborating with the AWS team to bring EESSI to their platform is very valuable.

ParallelCluster uses the infrastructure as code paradigm, and all that is needed to build a complete HPC cluster is a description of it in YAML format. In Figure 1, there is an example of a simple configuration file for ParallelCluster, where we specify the desired operating system, the machine instance types for both the head node and the compute nodes, among other configurations.

```
Image:
  Os: alinux2
HeadNode:
  InstanceType: t2.micro
  Networking:
    SubnetId: subnet-12345678
  Ssh:
    KeyName: ec2-key-name
Scheduling:
  Scheduler: slurm
  SlurmQueues:
    - Name: queue1
      Networking:
        SubnetIds:
          - subnet-12345678
  ComputeResources:
    - Name: compute-resource1
      InstanceType: c5.2xlarge
```

Figure 1: Example of ParallelCluster configuration file extracted from [ParallelCluster GitHub project](#)

Even though ParallelCluster dramatically simplifies the process of building an HPC cluster in the cloud, there are limitations with respect to more complex configurations. One of these limitations is the availability of scientific applications out of the box. The HPC cluster provided by AWS ParallelCluster comes with the necessary middleware (MPI, GPU drivers and libraries) and compilers but the applications must be compiled and installed by the end user. To

circumvent this limitation and others not addressed by ParallelCluster, [AWS maintains a GitHub repository of HPC recipes](#) [4] classified into different categories: storage, networking, environment, etc.

The Spack [5] team developed an environment recipe to tackle the software availability problem. It provides a configured Spack environment with which to install and compile software. But Spack is actually a software package manager, so users still need to compile their software stacks. On the other hand, our approach is to make the software available out of the box, without the need for any compilation or installation. We have developed an AWS recipe that automatically configures the cloud instances upon creation to expose all the software shipped with EESSI.

The recipe consists of a bash script hosted in the AWS recipes GitHub repository called [postinstall.sh](#). The script expects to be executed in a ParallelCluster operating system image, but it was designed to be easily adaptable to other systems. The main purpose of the script is to install CernVM-FS and configure it to make EESSI accessible from the cloud instances. Furthermore, it can optionally perform some other actions: set up a squid proxy server that caches recently used EESSI software for fast availability, or inject NVIDIA libraries and drivers into the EESSI stack, allowing EESSI-provided software to use the cloud instance GPU, in case it has one. Finally, we have also developed a way for EESSI to use the MPI stack of the host (which is officially the only one supported by AWS). In a standard EESSI installation, EESSI comes with its own MPI runtime that is used by default, but with the possibility, by design, of injecting an external one. Even though EESSI had this capability, until now it was not well documented how to make use of it. This initiative started as part of the AWS recipe, to allow EESSI to use the MPI layer supplied by ParallelCluster, but there are plans to make this feature part of the EESSI distribution, automating the procedure to perform this MPI injection in any EESSI installation.

For further information on how to make use of the recipe and more details about its features consult the [README at the GitHub repository](#).

In conclusion, we have successfully completed the development of the AWS recipe for EESSI integration into the AWS cloud, and presented a Pull Request that was accepted by the AWS team, as can be verified from Figure 2.

Recipe to install and configure EESSI #40

Merged mwvaughn merged 1 commit into [aws-samples:main](#) from [pfermi:eessi](#) on Nov 7

Conversation 1 | Commits 1 | Checks 0 | Files changed 8

pfermi commented on Oct 22

Description of changes:

Add a new recipe to the env namespace that provides the [EESSI](#) scientific software stack.

By submitting this pull request, I confirm that you can use, modify, copy, and redistribute this contribution, under the terms of your choice.

Recipe to install and configure EESSI a02f4b3

mwvaughn merged commit [a8a21f0](#) into [aws-samples:main](#) on Nov 7

mwvaughn commented on Nov 7

Thanks for the contribution!

Pull request successfully merged and closed

You're all set — the [pfermi:eessi](#) branch can be safely deleted.

If you wish, you can also delete this fork of [aws-samples/aws-hpc-recipes](#) in the [settings](#).

Figure 2: Screenshot of the [accepted Pull Request to AWS HPC recipes](#).

2.2 User accessibility to MultiXscale codes

To make the MultiXscale software easily accessible to users, we have decided to integrate the EESSI stack into Open OnDemand (OOD) [6]. OOD is an open-source project providing a web platform to interact with HPC clusters, primarily aiming to lower the entry-level barrier to such systems. Its presence in HPC centers has skyrocketed [7] in recent years, in part due to HPC users demanding these kind of tools, which let them better focus on their research.

We are on track to achieving this integration. We recently met the development team of OOD and we are aligned in working together to integrate EESSI into the OOD platform, and we agreed to meet periodically to monitor the development of this integration.

Finally, we should also highlight that there are EuroHPC JU centers, Deucalion and Vega, with both OOD and EESSI already installed. Therefore, once the development is completed, we will be able to test the OOD-EESSI integration in production systems.

3 Dissemination actions undergone in Task 7.2

The objective of Task 7.2 (Dissemination and communication activities) is to reach the maximum audience for the solutions developed by MultiXscale CoE. It involves both academia and industry from the scientific point of view and uses the tools developed here.

This task involves creating, updating, and maintaining the dissemination channels, demonstrating MultiXscale's presence at key events, and creating awareness through a continuous flow of information from the project activities to the community. The above-mentioned actions will be described in more detail in the following sections.

3.1 Dissemination channels

3.1.1 Webpage

The URL of the project website is <https://www.multixscale.eu/> (Figure 3). It is the central part of the dissemination activities and the face of the project, covering the entire spectrum of target audiences. The website is updated regularly according to the new content (deliverables, news items, tweets, etc.).

Figure 3: Screenshot of the current status of MultiXscale website (December 2024)

Several improvements have been made since the beginning of the project, starting with a fresher look and feel by involving a dedicated webmaster in the design update process. Additionally, more sections and subsections were added to complete the information on the website. In detail, these are:

- A new section on the main page called "News" shows the title and a thumbnail of the last ten posts from the MultiXscale blog. Their detail and the rest of the blog posts are listed in <https://www.multixscale.eu/blog-posts/>. At

the moment of writing this report, that section includes 39 entries.

- A new subsection under "About" category, including:
 - "Our mission", which shows a visual summary of the purpose of the project called [MultiXscale in a Nutshell](#).
 - [Organisation](#), describing the consortium structure and the Work Packages.
 - [Project Management Team](#) shows pictures, names, and e-mails of the project coordinator, the project manager, and the technical manager.
- A new section called "Software" on the main menu of the website, including one category for each of the scientific software developed in the CoE:
 - [ESPResSo](#).
 - [LAMMPS](#).
 - [waLBerla](#).
- A subsection under the "Outreach" category named [Dissemination](#) includes the dissemination material of the project: logo, brochure, posters, and slides.

3.1.2 Social media

Additionally to the website, the project information is also disseminated using social media to inform the audience about new publications, deliverables, presentations and events.

Five specific profiles have been created:

- [X/Twitter](#)
- [Youtube](#)
- [Facebook](#)
- [LinkedIn](#)
- [Bluesky](#)

All of them were created at the beginning of the project, except the Bluesky corporate profile, which was established at the end of the second year in M23 as a result of the suggestion proposed during the Communications Coffee Break organized by CASTIEL2. Other CoEs also agreed during the meeting to create new corporate profiles in Bluesky. For several reasons, some users are migrating from X/Twitter to other social media platforms, and Bluesky seems to be the reference alternative for this change.

New improved banners were also created especially for social media and have been updated on M20 on each corporate profile: X/Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, Facebook (find one example in Figure 4). The descriptions of each profile were also reviewed and improved in order to get more visibility. The Bluesky corporate profile already incorporated this branded content.

Table 1 summarizes the number of followers registered in December 2024 on each social media profile:

Social network	Followers	KPI (M24)	KPI (M48)
LinkedIn	564	150	300
X/Twitter	189	150	300
Youtube	94	150	300
Facebook	109	150	300
Bluesky	33	Not Applicable	Not Applicable

Table 1: Followers on each social network with a MultiXscale account. Numbers extracted on December 2024.

On LinkedIn, the milestone to get 300 followers, which was due for M48 at the end of the project, was achieved in M15. X / Twitter exceeded the number of followers due for M24. YouTube and Facebook were getting closer to this milestone. However, Facebook was identified as a complex platform to reach the target audience. Special actions were required to reach the audience in this channel. To improve the visibility of the Facebook profile and gain more followers, we started to publish stories and test different strategies to get successful results. We shared these difficulties during the CASTIEL2 Communications Coffee Breaks and other specific meetings like "EuroCC 2 Workshop event:

Figure 4: MutiXscale banner in X/Twitter social network

How to improve my NCC visibility", where the other participants agreed on the fact and shared experience: just a few corporate profiles of NCCs and CoEs have presence on Facebook, and the ones available have around 150 followers on average.

3.2 Dissemination strategy

The dissemination strategy followed by the MultiXscale CoE is centered on creating awareness since the beginning of the project. To follow the strategy, most of the consortium members were trained and motivated to disseminate the final or partial results in scientific and technical events. In the following subsections, the events with MultiXscale participation are listed.

3.2.1 Events

A complete dissemination of the project includes participation in different events, both at technical and scientific levels. MultiXscale participated during the reporting period in eighteen conferences, talks and workshops, being the most remarkable ones the [SC conference series](#) in the United States and the [ISC High Performance Computing](#), which took place in Germany, carrying out its participation in shared booths in collaboration with EuroHPC JU, project partners or other European projects. Additionally, MultiXscale dissemination team alongside other Centers of Excellence participated in the organization of [two workshops](#) in HiPEAC 25 conference, which will be focused in the paper of CoEs in the preparation of codes for the exascale era, encouraging a elevated number of women in HPC to represent their projects. More into detail, the attended events until M24 are reported in Table 2.

Status	Name	Action	Date	Target
Past	EuroHPC Summit week 2023	Poster	20-23 March 2023	Other EuroHPC projects, hardware vendors, funding agencies
Past	Easybuild user meeting	Training	24-26 April 2023	Academics and industrial users
Past	HPCKP Meeting 23	Training	17-18 May 2023	Academics and industrial users
Past	ISC High Performance 23	BoF and demo	21-25 May 2023	Cloud providers, HPC professionals, research software developers, hardware vendors
Past	Best Practices for CernVM-FS in HPC	Training	Autumn 4 December 2023	EuroHPC JU system administrators
Past	Online Tutorial: EESSI	Training	5 Dec. 2023	Users and HPC professionals
Past	Advanced Computing User Day	Talk	7 Dec. 2023	Users in research and business
Past	XI Jornades de Bioinformatica i Genomica	Poster	15 Dec. 2023	Academics
Past	de RSE24	Training	5-7 March 2024	Researchers

Past	EuroHPC Summit week 2024	Poster and demo	8-21 2024	March	Other EuroHPC projects, hardware vendors, funding agencies
Past	4th Baltic HPC and Cloud Conference	Poster	11-12	April 2024	Research communities that use HPC, students, HPC experts, and industry
Past	HPCKP Meeting 24	Training	8-9	May 2024	Academics and industrial users
Past	ISC High Performance 24	Poster and demo	14	May 2024	Cloud providers, HPC professionals, research software developers, hardware vendors
Past	Teratec Forum	Poster	29-30	May 2024	Industry, users and HPC professionals
Past	Austrian-Slovenian HPC Meeting	Poster and talk	11-13	June 2024	Scientists and technicians
Past	InPEX Workshop	Contribution to the “Software production and management” topic of the workshop	17-19	June 2024	From researchers and engineers to policy organizations and funding bodies
Past	OpenModel Exploitation Workshop	Invited talk	18	September 2024	Academic users
Past	Nordic Industry Days	Talk	2-3	September 2024	Industry, users and HPC professionals
Past	Sprint Training Event: Introduction to EESSI	Training	4	October 2024	Users and HPC professionals
Past	ESPreSo Summer School. “Simulating soft matter across scales”	Training	7-11	October 2024	Academic users
Past	EuroHPC User Day	Demo	22-23	October 2024	Users and HPC professionals
Past	Dutch Federated Computing and Data workshop	Talk	15	November 2024	Users and HPC professionals
Past	EPICURE webinar	Training	15	November 2024	Users and HPC professionals
Past	Supercomputing	BoF session and demos	18-22	November 2024	Industry, users and HPC professionals
Past	NRIS Talks	Training	28	November 2024	Users and HPC professionals
Past	SLING days	Hackathon	3-5	December 2024	Researchers and students
Past	EPICURE webinar	Training	13	December 2024	Users and HPC professionals
Planned	HIPEAC 25	Demo, talks, workshop organization	20-22	January 2025	Researchers, industry representatives, students
Planned	EuroHPC Summit week 2025	Poster and demos	18-20	March 2025	Other EuroHPC projects, hardware vendors, funding agencies
Planned	HPCKP Meeting 25	Demo (submitted)	4-5	June 2025	Academics and industrial users
Planned	ISC High Performance 25	Tutorial and BoF (submitted)	10-13	June 2025	Cloud providers, HPC professionals, research software developers, hardware vendors
Planned	Supercomputing 25	TBD	16-21	November 2025	Industry, users and HPC professionals

Table 2: List of past and planned events to disseminate MultiXscale project.

Other activities

The interaction with CASTIEL2 continues not only with the participation at the monthly Communications Coffee Breaks, but also with the CoEs & NCCs specific Slack channel, that gathers 145 participants from other communication departments, a good platform for the exchange of information and ideas, and also with the participation in the following specific sessions:

- "Leveraging LinkedIn & Google (including paid ads) to interact with industry & Awareness Creation in general about HPC- Experience from NCC Luxembourg", organized on 13th March 2024.
- "Pimp my LinkedIn profile: Internal workshop for the EuroCC community", organized by NCC Austria on 10th June 2024.
- "1st legal support webinar-Joint controllership of personal data in European, multinational projects-case example LUMI", organized by NCC Finland on 4th September 2024.
- "How to improve my NCC visibility", organized by EuroCC PMT on 10th September 2024

3.3 Press strategy

Press releases, announcements and relevant information produced by MultiXscale project have been sent periodically for publication to the media and specialized magazines and portals.

In addition, representatives of MultiXscale project attending the events mentioned above took advantage of the networking sessions organized with journalists to transmit the achievements of the project to reach the target audience.

All the press impacts registered are available on the [Media-coverage](#) subsection in "Outreach" category.

3.3.1 Press releases and newsletters

Two [press releases](#) were issued during the relevant period. They were distributed to the media and included in the newsletter published twice per year.

[The first press release](#) was prepared and launched at the beginning of the project on 30th March 2023 linked to the the kick-off meeting. Several impacts on the media were identified as a result of the press conference organized for the journalists. [The second press release](#) was launched to the media on March 13th to announce the MultiXscale General Assembly carried out from 21st to 22nd March 2024 in Antwerp, Belgium.

Regarding the [MultiXscale newsletters](#), three issues were already released: two in 2023 and one in 2024. The second issue of 2024 due by the end of December is still under preparation. The issues were published on MultiXscale webpage, announced on social media and disseminated by email to the subscription list created for this purpose.

A new press release is being prepared in collaboration with HPCwire and EuroHPC JU. It is related to the HPCwire Readers' Choice Awards 2024, recently received by EESSI, and it will highlight, among others, the contribution made by MultiXscale to EESSI.

Additionally, a podcast is also being prepared in collaboration with NCC Belgium. It will be recorded by the end of December 2024 or early in January 2025. It will be published as soon as it is ready and scheduled in the platform HPC Podcast for "Supercomputing in Europe. EuroCC and CoE Network".

3.3.2 Publication in scientific journals

Results obtained during the MultiXscale project will be submitted for publication to top-level peer-reviewed international journals. The partners have preidentified a list of journals in which publications could be presented:

- Journal of Chemical Physics (Impact factor (2023): 3.1)
- Computer Physics Communications (Impact factor (2023): 7.2)
- Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation (Impact factor (2024): 5.7)
- Journal of Computational Physics (Impact factor (2023): 3.8)

Besides, the results will be submitted to other journals identified as relevant in the field, such as Faraday Discussions, where one of the publications was registered in the reporting period.

To date, the following [publications](#) have been registered:

- David Beyer, Paola B. Torres, Sebastian P. Pineda, Claudio F. Narambuena, Jean-Noël Grad, Peter Košovan, Pablo M. Blanco; pyMBE: The Python-based molecule builder for ESPResSo. *J. Chem. Phys.* 14 July 2024; 161 (2): 022502. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0216389>
- El Hassane Lahrar, Céline Merlet; Investigating the effect of particle size distribution and complex exchange dynamics on NMR spectra of ions diffusing in disordered porous carbons through a mesoscopic model. *Faraday Discussions* 29 May 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D4FD00082J>
- Morillo, J. et al. (2025). Preparing to Hit the Ground Running: Adding RISC-V Support to EESSI. In: Weiland, M., Neuwirth, S., Kruse, C., Weinzierl, T. (eds) High Performance Computing. ISC High Performance 2024 International Workshops. ISC High Performance 2023. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 15058. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-73716-9_21
- Goth F, Alves R, Braun M et al. Foundational Competencies and Responsibilities of a Research Software Engineer (version 1; peer review: 1 approved). *F1000Research* 2024, 13:1429. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.157778.1>
- Alan O’Cais, Kenneth Hoste, Jean-Noël Grad, Caspar van Leeuwen, Lara Peeters, Satish Kamath, Thomas Röblitz, Richard Topouchian, Bob Dröge, Pedro Santos Neves, Rudolf Weeber; Portable test run of ESPResSo on EuroHPC systems via EESSI. Accepted to be published in the EuroHPC 2nd edition of proceedings of Computer Science, Elsevier. December 2024

4 Sustainability plan status update (Task 7.3)

4.1 Current status

Task 7.3 focuses on the sustainability of the outputs of the CoE. This involves including external partners trained to support MultiXscale users professionally. It also includes designing a certification program for external partners to guarantee their competencies using tools and codes from MultiXscale. Lastly, it provides for the exploration of the creation of a legal entity. This task is still in exploratory status, centering all the efforts accounted for in the second half of the project.

4.2 Technical and scientific support

Technical support is already available at the [EESSI GitLab project](#). Its design and functionalities were defined at the beginning of the project in Work Package 5 (Building, Supporting and Maintaining a Central Shared Stack of Optimized Scientific Software Installations). During the project execution, all the WP5 partners will rotate the dedication to the support desk every two weeks. Once the project finishes, a dedicated support team is expected to handle the support desk. However, the scope of such ongoing support has to be redefined in the following months according to the outcomes of the sustainability task.

Scientific codes created during the evolution of Work Packages 2 to 4 are not excluded from the sustainability plan, but they are still unexplored due to their current maturity.

4.3 Legal entities

The creation of a legal entity to ensure the future sustainability of the project’s outcomes is started to be investigated. Some examples of entities to be explored are:

- [European Research Infrastructure Consortium \(ERIC\)](#).
- [European Economic Interest Grouping](#).
- [European Cooperative Society](#).

These entities provide a distinct legal identity, enabling them to own assets, enter into contracts, and manage finances independently. This legal framework offers stability and predictability, which are crucial for sustainability. Additionally, those have international recognition, facilitating cross-border collaborations and partnerships with other research institutions and organizations, and can secure dedicated funding from various sources, including public funds, private investments, and user fees, which are key to provide professional support once the project finishes.

5 Status of the adoption of MultiXscale codes by industry (Task 7.4)

Task 7.4 focuses on disseminating the CoE services among future users inside the HPC community. To fulfill the objective of the aforementioned task, it is necessary to provide targeted training to the key sectors of the HPC industry,

which will profit from the services and codes created in MultiXscale CoE.

In more detail, training activities will be conducted in two sessions covering two topics. One will be centered on cloud providers and industrial cloud users, and the other will cover the usage of the codes developed by the CoE in the industry.

The first mentioned session will show the outcomes of Work Package 5 (Building, Supporting and Maintaining a Central Shared Stack of Optimized Scientific Software Installations) and Work Package 7, Task 7.1 (Scientific applications provisioned on demand). This session will show how to build, update and use the software stack in a cloud environment. Current technical advances make MultiXscale ready to showcase the deployment of EESSI in Amazon Web Services, as described in the section of this document referring to Task 7.1. A cloud-agnostic solution using Magic Castle is currently used to provide a training environment [8] described in Deliverable 6.2. The target audience for this training is people with technical roles using cloud services, independently of their expertise. Additionally, cloud vendors will also benefit from this session, as they will be able to promote their solutions to the attendees.

The second session will show the advancements done by MultiXscale CoE in the development of new codes for scientific software and their exascale scope to industrial users. The expected outcome of this training is to ensure the technology transfer of the codes to the industry and its proper usage at different scales. The scientific development of the new codes is done in Work Packages 2 (Preparation and optimization of community software codes toward the Exascale-readiness) and 3 (Development and efficient implementation of interfaces for coupling different length scales).

5.1 Strategy

Although the development of scientific and technical tasks is evolving as expected in the timeframe of the project, their current status limits the possibility to perform the training sessions before Q3 of 2025. However, dissemination activities, discussed in Section 3, are targeted to find potential attendees and create awareness of our activities and development.

Specifically, the planned activities for the first half of 2025 are:

- HiPEAC 25 (Barcelona, January):
 - Keynote about the project, technical talk, and technical demo.
 - Targeting cloud providers and users.
- EuroHPC Summit (Kraków, March):
 - Poster to be accepted, and a demo to be defined.
 - Targeting both cloud providers and users, and industrial scientists participating in other European projects.
- HPCCKP 25 (Barcelona, June):
 - MultiXscale general training, targeting academy and industry.
 - Targeting both cloud providers and users, and industrial scientists.
- ISC 25 (Hamburg, May):
 - A tutorial submission has been sent.
 - Birds of a Feather proposal sent.
 - Demo at Azure and AWS booths.
 - Demos at HPCNow! (Do IT Now) booth.
 - Targeting both cloud providers and users, and industrial scientists.

Topics of interest to the attendees of these events will be gathered and used to build the agenda of industry-oriented training, ensuring that the content will be well received by them. The expected dates for those sessions are:

- Cloud providers and users: Q3-Q4 2025.
- Scientific developments: Q1-Q2 2026.

A final deliverable in M40 will contain the outcomes of those two sessions (agenda, statistics, feedback, and other information of interest).

5.2 Corporate interest

The dissemination activities performed since the beginning of the project, plus the awareness created by formal and informal talks from MultiXscale scientists and technical staff, have positioned the MultiXscale CoE firmly in the EuroHPC ecosystem. Partners from Leonardo, one of the consortium members, have shown their interest in the new codes for helicopter design, which will be able to execute exascale simulations in the future. A pharmaceutical company also expressed interest in the latest codes for biomedical applications of ultrasound, which will be used to treat rare diseases.

At the technical level, cloud computing services such as Amazon Web Services and Azure are already collaborating with the development of the tools and services developed in this project.

6 Conclusion and outlook

The dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities performed during the first half of the project had a positive outcome. The CoE is readily identified among the other CoEs, and external researchers and users close to the project clearly recognize its outputs and potential ways for collaboration. Additionally, people involved in the CoE are associated with MultiXscale thanks to a distinctive brand used in events such as EuroHPC Summit Week, which provides a picture of cohesion and teamwork.

The four tasks from Work Package 7 pursue user-friendly access to the solutions provided by the CoE (Task 7.1), disseminate MultiXscale's outcomes and image (Task 7.2), ensure the project's future (Task 7.3), and train future users of the tools and codes developed during the project's execution.

Regarding Task 7.1, the initial idea was to provide a cloud agnostic solution from the beginning of its execution. It is mostly complete by the use of Magic Castle, as it is described in Deliverable 6.2 "Infrastructure to support training activities". However, the market request for a software provisioning tool for AWS ParallelCluster made the MultiXscale team develop a native solution for AWS, with the objective to boost the adoption of the solution by the HPC cloud users. That decision agrees also with the training session expected at the Q3-Q4 of 2025, as it is described in Section 5. Additionally, the integration of EESSI with HPC portals is starting to be investigated. Regular meetings with Open OnDemand developers are now scheduled to find the appropriate way to provide the two solutions together.

Task 7.2 was centered in the dissemination of the activities of the CoE and the organization of new ones. The low Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the scientific codes at the beginning of the project have limited the number of scientific events where MultiXscale results could be presented. It is expected to increase the number of scientific dissemination activities during the second half of the project, as the developed codes will be more mature. The dissemination team actively participated, alongside others CoEs such as MaX, ChEESE, ESIWACE, POP3 and others, in the organization of two workshops centered in Centers of Excellence at the HiPEAC conference with a strong presence of women in the agenda. Last, dissemination channels were updated to the current trends with the creation of a [Bluesky](#) account, as a common idea born in a communication coffee break session organized by CASTIEL2.

Task 7.3 is the one of the lesser developed tasks to date. The project members involved are investigating the most appropriate way to ensure the sustainability of the projects, and in particular the creation of a legal entity that will take care of providing all the needed resources to the outputs from MultiXscale execution.

Lastly, Task 7.4 will ensure the adoption of MultiXscale codes by the industry, providing two workshops, one targeting cloud users and cloud providers (referred some lines above) and another one covering the scientific developments and targeting the industry. Those workshops are expected to happen around M36, so there is enough time to find the appropriate diffusion channels to reach the maximum number of people and expect a high attendance.

In summary, dissemination, communication and exploitation activities are evolving according to the expected pace.

References

Acronyms used

AWS Amazon Web Services
EESSI European Environment for Scientific Software Installations
HPC High Performance Computing
CoE Center of Excellence

Software mentioned

Magic Castle Magic Castle
OOD Open OnDemand

URLs referenced

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<https://www.multixscale.eu/deliverables> ... <https://www.multixscale.eu/deliverables>
Internal Project Management Link ... <https://github.com/multixscale/planning/issues/73>
elisabeth.ortega@hpcnow.com ... <mailto:elisabeth.ortega@hpcnow.com>
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accepted Pull Request to AWS HPC recipes ... <https://github.com/aws-samples/aws-hpc-recipes/pull/4>

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AWS maintains a GitHub repository of HPC recipes ... <https://github.com/aws-samples/aws-hpc-recipes>
[postinstall.sh](https://github.com/aws-samples/aws-hpc-recipes/blob/main/recipes/env/eessi/assets/postinstall.sh) ... <https://github.com/aws-samples/aws-hpc-recipes/blob/main/recipes/env/eessi/assets/postinstall.sh>
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MultiXscale in a Nutshell ... <https://www.multixscale.eu/multixscale-in-a-nutshell/>
Organisation ... <https://www.multixscale.eu/organisation/>
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